
**Geographical Indication (GI) Tagged Agricultural Products in
Maharashtra: Regional & Temporal Analysis**

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Abstract:

A geographical indication (GI) is a sign used on products that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities or a reputation that are due to that origin. Geographical Indication Protection is granted to a group of manufacturers, who belong to a particular location, where the good was first originated. It has positive effect on agricultural products in several ways including increased income, increased consumer trust and better marketing etc. Geographical indication is a major tool for rural development. India had 643 registered GI products and out of 643 products, 199 products lie in the agriculture sector. The Contribution of Maharashtra in GI is mainly in agricultural products. As of 2024, Maharashtra had 52 registered GI products and out of 52, 36 products lie in the agriculture sector. Most of the GI tagged agricultural products in Maharashtra observed in the region of Western Maharashtra (Pune division) and Konkan.

Keywords: Geographical Indication, GI Tag, Intellectual Property Right, Region

Introduction:

Geographical Indication is different from other IPRs like Patent, Trademarks and designs. Geographical Indication Protection is granted to a group of manufacturers, who belong to a particular location, where the good was first originated. There are many determinants of GI products such as place of origin, climate, topography, human work of a particular geographical location). As per Section 2(1)(e) of the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999, “a geographical indication refers to an indication capable of identifying goods, including natural goods, agricultural goods, or manufactured goods, as manufactured or originating in a country’s territory, or a locality or region within that territory, where a specific

quality, reputation, or any other attribute of such good is particularly a characteristic to its geographical origin. In the case of manufactured goods, one of the activities corresponding to the processing, production, or preparation of goods, should take place in the territory, region, or locality”. Indian GI Act came into force with effect from 15 September 2003 (Moudgil, 2021).

Geographical indication is a major tool for rural development. It protects the Intellectual Property rights associated with agricultural products originating in specific geographical region. It helps in creating relationship between the agricultural products and the area to which it belongs. The unique agricultural products of rural communities associated with GI needs for rural development. GI tag provides legal

protection to the product and also prevents unauthorized use of GI tag products by others. GI tag helps consumers to get quality product. There are three types of geographical indication like protected designation of origin, protected geographical indication and traditional specialties guaranteed (Jasani, Mayani.2023). GI tagged product has certain status which is not only famous for its characteristics but it also becomes globally acceptable.

India had 643 registered GI products and out of 643 products, 199 products lie in the agriculture sector. States such as Karnataka, West Bengal, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Maharashtra (to name just a few) have put India on the „GI map“ with major agricultural product. The Contribution of Maharashtra in GI is mainly in agricultural products. As of 2024, Maharashtra had 52 registered GI products and out of 52, 36 products lie in the agriculture sector.

Objective:

To analyses regional and temporal variation in Geographical Indication (GI) tagged agricultural products in Maharashtra

Database and Methodology:

The present research work is totally based on secondary source of information. It has been collected from government website and publication etc.

Temporal & Regional Variations in Geographical Indication (GI) tagged agricultural products in Maharashtra:

Maharashtra which is located in the western peninsular region of India, has a wide range of geographical and cultural diversity which helps to produce number of GI tagged products in agricultural, handicrafts and food stuff etc. The Contribution of Maharashtra in GI is mainly in agricultural products. As of 2024, Maharashtra had 35 registered GI products and out of 35, 27 products lie in the agriculture sector.

Though, the GI registration process in India started in 2004-05, first agricultural products was registered in 2010-11 in Maharashtra. In 2010-11, 02 agricultural products namely Strawberry from Mahabaleshwar of Satara District and Grapes from Nashik District got GI tagged first time in history of Maharashtra. In 2013-14, again 02 agricultural products namely Jaggery-Kolhapur and Orange-Nagpur got GI tag.

Maharashtra: GI Tagged Products in Agricultural Sector (2004-2024)

Sr. No.	Year	Number of Registration in Agricultural Products	Product Name with District	Region/ Administrative Division
1	2010-2011	02	Strawberry-Mahabaleshwar- Satara	Pune Division
			Grape-Nashik	Nashik Division
2	2013-2014	02	Jaggery-Kolhapur	Pune Division
			Orange-Nagpur	Nagpur Division
3	2015-2016	07	Ajara Ghansal Rice-Kolhapur	Pune Division
			Mangalwedha Jowar-Solapur	Pune Division
			Kokum- Sindhudurg & Ratnagiri	Konkan Division
			Waghya Ghevada-Satara	Pune Division
			Navapur Tur Dal-Nandurbar	Nashik Division
			Vengurla Cashew-Sindhudurg	Konkan Division
			Lasalgaon Onion-Nashik	Nashik Division
4	2016-2017	12	Sangli Raisins-Sangli	Pune Division
			Beed Custard Apple-Beed	Aurangabad Division
			Jalna Sweet Orange-Jalna	Aurangabad Division
			Waigaon Turmeric-Wardha	Nagpur Division
			Purandar Fig-Pune	Pune Division
			Jalgaon Bharit Brinjal- Jalgaon	Nashik Division
			Solapur Pomegranate- Solapur	Pune Division
			Bhiwapur Chilli-Nagpur	Nagpur Division
			Ambemohar Rice-Pune	Pune Division
			Dahanu Gholvad Chikoo-Palghar	Konkan Division
			Jalgaon Banana- Jalgaon	Nashik Division
			Marathwada Kesar Mango-Marathwada	Aurangabad Division
5	2018-2019	02	Alphonso-Konkan	Konkan Division
			Sangli Turmeric-Sangli	Pune Division
6	2022-2023	01	Alibag White Onion-Raigad	Konkan Division
7	2023-2024 (Till 31 st December 2024)	10	Bhandara Chinoor Rice-Bhandara	Nagpur Division
			Vasmat Haldi (Turmeric)-Hingoli	Aurangabad Division
			Nandurbar Amchur- Nandurbar	Nashik Division
			Nandurbar Mirchi -Nandurbar	Nashik Division
			Panchincholi Tamarind-Latur	Aurangabad Division
			Borsuri Tur Dal-Latur	Aurangabad Division
			Kasti Coriander-Latur	Aurangabad Division
			Badlapur Jamun-Thane	Konkan Division
			Bahadoli Jamun-Palghar	Konkan Division
			Dagdi Jowar of Jalna-Jalna	Aurangabad Division
	Total	36		

Source: compiled by researcher

In the year 2015-16 total 07 agricultural products got GI tag. They were namely Ajara Ghansal Rice-Kolhapur, Mangalwedha Jowar-Solapur, Kokum-Sindhudurg & Ratnagiri, Waghya Ghevada-Satara, Navapur Tur Dal-Nandurbar, Vengurla Cashew-Sindhudurg and Lasalgaon Onion-Nashik. Year 2016-17 was historical and memorable year for Maharashtra because in this year total 12 agricultural products were registered under GI tag. They were namely Sangli Raisins-Sangli, Beed Custard Apple-Beed, Jalna Sweet Orange-Jalna, Waigaon Turmeric-Wardha, Purandar Fig-Pune, Jalgaon Bharit Brinjal- Jalgaon, Solapur Pomegranate-Solapur, Bhiwapur Chilli-Nagpur, Ambemohar Rice-Pune, Dahanu Gholvad Chikoo-Palghar, Jalgaon Banana- Jalgaon, and Marathwada Kesar Mango-Marathwada. In the year 2018-19 02 agricultural products namely Alphonso-Konkan and Sangli Turmeric- Sangli got GI tag. In the year 2022-23 only one agricultural product got GI tag, that was Alibag White Onion-Raigad. Recently in the year 2023-24 total 10 GI tag were registered in agricultural products.

Maharashtra: Region (Administrative Division) wise GI Tagged Products in Agricultural Sector (2004-2024)

Sr. No	Region / Administrative Division	Number of Registration in Agricultural Products
1	Konkan Division	07
2	Nashik Division	07
3	Pune Division	10
4	Aurangabad Division	08
5	Amravati Division	00
6	Nagpur Division	04
	Total	36

Source: compiled by researcher

Pune division which is generally termed as Western Maharashtra has registered highest number of GI tag in

Maharashtra. Total 10 GI tags in agricultural sector have been registered in this division. It is due to its favourable geographical condition, fertile soil, irrigation facilities, favourable climate etc. this region has registered highest number of GI tag in agricultural products in Maharashtra. Pune is followed by Aurangabad division (Marathwada region) with 08 GI tags. Konkan and Nashik division both have registered 07 GI tags in agricultural products respectively. Both these regions have special geographical condition which is suitable for specific crops like Kokum, Alphonso Mango, Banana, and Cashew etc. Due to adverse geographical condition for agriculture Nagpur and Amravati division (Vidarbha Region) have less number of GI tag in agriculture products. Nagpur division has 04 GI tags only. Amravati which is part of vidarbha region doesn't have any single GI tag in agriculture products.

Conclusion:

There are many determinants of GI products such as place of origin, climate, topography and human work of a particular geographical location etc. GI tag has positive effect on agricultural products in several ways including increased income, increased consumer trust and better marketing etc. It is helpful for economic growth in the region, better employment opportunities in the region and for overall rural development. Maharashtra has good potential for getting GI tag in agricultural products. However, Out of 643 GI registrations in India, only 52 GI registrations are found in Maharashtra State and Out of 52, only 36 registrations are found in agricultural products. It clearly indicates that, comparatively people of Maharashtra are not so aware of the GI tag Registration process. Pune division has registered highest number of GI tag in Maharashtra. It is due to its favourable

geographical condition, fertile soil, irrigation facilities, favourable climate etc. On the other hand, Due to adverse geographical condition for agriculture Nagpur and Amravati division (Vidarbha Region) have less number of GI tags in agriculture products.

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